

Studies on Thin Layer Chromatographic Separation of some Sulpha Drugs

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Some sulpha drugs in the form of their coupled products with 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione and 4-hydroxy-2-methylthio-6-methylpyrimidine have been separated and identified. In order to achieve better separations these studies have been carried out using surfactants as mobile phase as well as impregnant in adsorbents.

Sulpha drugs have been separated by various paper and thin layer chromatographic techniques. There are reports on such technique using alumina as adsorbent¹, *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediammonium dichloride as a coupling agent², chloroform-*n*-butanol-light petroleum³, using diazotisation coupling technique⁴, silica gel impregnated with cadmium acetate and using acetoacetanilide as a coupling agent⁶.

The present paper describes the resolution and identification of some sulpha drugs in the form of coupled products with 5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (1) and 4-hydroxy-2-methylthio-6-methylpyrimidine (2). In order to achieve better separations, these studies have been carried out on surfactant impregnated plates as well as using surfactants as mobile phase.

Results and Discussion

When sulpha drugs were spotted individually or as a mixture, on subsequent development they were distinctly separated.

Separation of coupled products of sulpha drugs with 5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione : For the resolution of these coupled products various solvents and surfactants were employed. A 2% Tween-20 was found to be the best solvent for the separation of these coupled products. In solutions of 2% Triton X-405 and 2% Tween-40 good separation could not be achieved and tailing was observed with some of the compounds. With solvent systems 1% Tween-20, 1% Triton X-405, 1% Tween-80, 3% Triton X-405, 2% Tween-80, 1% Tween-40, separation was clear but all coupled products could not be separated. With cationic surfactants i.e. cetylpyridinium chloride, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and tetrabutylammonium bromide good separations could not be achieved. Anionic surfactants also could not resolve the mixture of sulphonamides (Table 1). Better separation while using surfactants as mobile phase may be due to formation of surfactant-drug derivative complex⁷ (3). However, relatively better separation in non-ionic surfactants may be attributed to the hydration of non-ionic surfactant solutions.

These coupled products could be observed directly as

yellow coloured spots.

Separation of coupled products of sulpha drugs with 4-hydroxy-2-methylthio-6-methylpyrimidine : For the resolution of these coupled products, surfactants were used as mobile phase as well for the impregnation of stationary phase. Silica gel impregnated with 2% sodium dodecyl sulphate was found to be the best adsorbent

TABLE 1— R_f ($\times 100$) VALUES OF SOME SULPHA DRUGS AS THEIR COUPLED PRODUCTS WITH 5,5-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXAN-1,3-DIONE

Sulpha drug	Silica gel G					
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Depson	23	50	51	53	47	50
Septan	46	60	64	65	62	61
Metakelfin	42	53	70	63	60	64
Orsul	34	58	52	68	62	58
Urobiotic	41	65	54	73	58	62
Sulphaacetamide	51	77	69	84	75	72
Sulphadiazene	30	46	32	33	40	35
Sulphadimidine	32	30	33	32	30	36
Sulphaguanidine	48	34	43	39	41	72

*Solvent systems : (1) = 1% Tween-20; (2) = 2% Tween-20; (3) = 1% cetyltrimethylammonium bromide; (4) = 1% Tween-80; (5) = 2% Tween-80; (6) = 2% Tween-40.

best for the separation of sulpha drugs as their azothiopyrimidine derivatives (Table 2). Silica gel impregnated with 2% Tween-20, 1% cetylpyridinium

TABLE 2— R_f ($\times 100$) VALUES OF SOME SULPHONAMOYLAZOTHIOPYRIMIDINES*

Sulpha drug	Silica gel G					Silica gel + 2% Tween-20 (6)	Silica gel + 1% Cetyl pyridinium chloride (6)	+ Silica gel + 2% Sodium dodecyl sulphate (6)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)			
Sulphamethoxazole	2.7	61	79	56	70	72	66	73
Sulphamethopyrazine	3.4	56	76	51	74	74	63	77
Sulphaphenozole	6.2	52	54	54	72	73	60	82
Sulphamaxole	26	63	56	55	67	38	58	89
Sulphadiazene	27	24	75	63	80	47	69	53
Sulphaguanidine	0.0	72	77	72	54	54	49	43
Sulphanilamide	18	58	73	54	62	35	52	50
Sulphamethizole	21	58	91	51	64	42	6.6	56
Sulphadoxine	19	54	81	48	72	40	61	60
Sulphadimethoxime	22	73	83	58	66	53	59	76

*Solvent systems : (1) = 100 ml hexane + 40 ml chloroform; (2) = 0.01% Tween-20; (3) = 60 ml chloroform + 20 ml acetone + 10 ml benzene; (4) = 0.01% sodium dodecyl sulphate; (5) = 0.01% cetyl pyridinium chloride; (6) = 60 ml chloroform + 20 ml acetone.

chloride, 0.2% sodium dodecylsulphate, 1% sodium dodecylsulphate, 0.2% cetylpyridinium chloride did not effect good separations and profuse tailing was observed with the majority of compounds. The best solvent system for development was found to be chloroform + acetone (60 : 20) for surfactant impregnated plates, whereas 0.01% cetylpyridinium chloride is the best solvent system for silica gel plates in which all the sulpha drugs could be separated. However, the separation is more clear without any tailing when 2% sodium dodecyl sulphate impregnated silica gel G plates were employed using chloroform + acetone (60 : 20) as the mobile phase. Surprisingly, when using 1% Tween-20 in water as mobile phase very good results were observed and nine out of ten sulpha drugs could be resolved. The azothiopyrimidine derivatives of sulpha drugs could be observed directly as coloured spots.

The improvement in separation using surfactant impregnated plates or when surfactant was used as mobile phase, may be due to the formation of surfactant drug derivative complex (4) which has different mobility for different compounds.

Formation of similar surfactant-drug derivative complex has also been reported by other workers⁸.

In general, the mobility of compounds on silica gel G impregnated with surfactant was enhanced when compared to that on silica gel G. Similarly, mobility of sulpha drug derivatives was much higher when surfactants was used as mobile phase.

Experimental

All the solvents used were freshly dried and distilled. Glass plates (20 cm × 20 cm) were used. An ascending irrigation technique was employed.

Coupled products of sulpha drugs with 5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione : Sulpha drug (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) was added to it. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (10.0 g) and 5,5-dimethylcyclohexan-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The resulting solid products were washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as yellow orange crystals : depson, m.p. 215°; septan, 204°; metakelfin, 200°; orisul, 215°; urobiotic, 222°; sulpha acetamide, 140°; sulphadiazene, 114°; sulphadimidine, 217°; sulpha guanidine, 210°.

Coupled products of sulpha drugs with 4-hydroxy-2-methylthio-6-methylpyrimidine : Sulpha drug (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) was added to it. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered in a pre-cooled solution of 4-hydroxy-2-methylthio-6-methylpyrimidine (0.01 mol) in 10% NaOH (10 ml) containing sodium ac-

etate (3 g). The resulting solid products were washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as yellow to brown crystals : sulpha methoxazole, m.p. 210°; sulphamethopyrazine, 220°; sulphaphenazole, 197°; sulphamoxole, 224°; sulphadiazene, 174°; sulphaguanidine, 212°; sulphanilamide, 195°; sulphamethizole, 211°; sulphadoxime, 159°; sulphadimethoxine, 115°.

The following adsorbents were employed : silica gel G (E. Merck); silica gel G with 2% Tween-20; silica gel G with 0.2% sodium dodecyl sulphate; silica gel G with 0.2% cetylpyridinium chloride, silica gel G with 1% cetylpyridinium chloride; silica gel G with 2% sodium dodecyl sulphate; silica gel G with 4% sodium dodecyl sulphate.

The solutions of hydrazono and azopyrimidine derivatives were spotted on the tlc plates and left for 1 h at room temperature, after which they were developed with suitable solvents. It took about 35 min for the solvent system to migrate 15 cm and coloured spots could be observed without visualising agents.

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